

Correlation between Mortality with Pro-BNP Levels and Precipitating Factors of Acute Heart Failure in Patients Presenting to a Medical Emergency of Tertiary Care Hospital: An Observational Study

Rajnish Kumar¹, Ravi Vishnu Prasad², Santosh Kumar³

¹Senior Resident, Department of General Medicine, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar

²Professor & HOD, Department of Cardiology, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar

³Senior Resident, Department of General Medicine, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Santosh Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Acute heart failure (AHF) is a significant public health concern with high morbidity and mortality rates. In the Indian context, the burden of heart failure is increasing, necessitating effective tools for early diagnosis and risk stratification. B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP) and its precursor, N-terminal pro-BNP (NT-proBNP), have emerged as crucial biomarkers in the management of heart failure, providing valuable prognostic information.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the correlation between mortality, NT-proBNP levels, and precipitating factors of acute heart failure.

Methods: A total of 200 patients with acute heart failure were included. Data were collected through patient interviews, clinical examinations, and laboratory tests, including NT-proBNP levels. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to identify predictors of mortality and to analyze the correlation between NT-proBNP levels and patient outcomes.

Results: The study found a significant positive correlation between elevated NT-proBNP levels and increased mortality in patients with acute heart failure ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$). Mortality rates were significantly higher in patients with NT-proBNP levels above 2000 pg/mL. Logistic regression analysis identified NT-proBNP levels >2000 pg/mL, age >65 years, and a history of coronary artery disease as significant independent predictors of mortality. Common precipitating factors for acute heart failure included acute myocardial infarction (40%) and arrhythmias (25%).

Conclusion: The study concludes that higher NT-proBNP levels are strongly associated with increased mortality in patients with acute heart failure. Age and history of coronary artery disease are also significant predictors of mortality. These findings underscore the importance of NT-proBNP as a prognostic tool in the emergency department for risk stratification and guiding clinical management.

Recommendations: The integration of NT-proBNP testing into standard clinical protocols in tertiary care settings is recommended to enhance the early identification and management of high-risk patients. Further research is needed to explore cost-effective strategies for the broader implementation of NT-proBNP testing in routine clinical practice in India.

Keywords: Acute Heart Failure, NT-proBNP, Mortality, Prognostic Biomarker, Risk Stratification.

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Introduction

AHF is a serious medical illness with a significant risk of morbidity and death and a quick onset of symptoms. Because cardiovascular disorders are so common in India, the burden of AHF is especially high. In order to enhance patient outcomes, timely diagnosis and efficient risk stratification are essential components of AHF care. (NT-proBNP), the precursor of (BNP), has become one of the most important indicators for the diagnosis and treatment of heart failure. When it comes to the

diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment planning of patients suffering from acute decompensated heart failure (ADHF), these indicators are indispensable in the emergency room.

A biomarker known as NT-proBNP is secreted by the heart ventricles in reaction to elevated wall stress. In individuals with heart failure, elevated levels of NT-proBNP are predictive of worse outcomes and are an indication of cardiac dysfunction. The significance of NT-proBNP in

predicting mortality and directing treatment strategies in AHF has been reaffirmed by recent research. For example, NT-proBNP levels are highly linked with in-hospital and long-term mortality in patients with heart failure. Elevated NT-proBNP levels were strongly linked to higher mortality, highlighting their predictive significance in clinical practice [1].

The use of NT-proBNP in the treatment of heart failure has been the subject of increasing research in India. According to a research done in which NT-proBNP can accurately predict death and morbidity in Indian patients who have heart failure. This study provided strong evidence for the prognostic importance of NT-proBNP in the Indian setting by showing that higher levels were significantly linked to increased short- and long-term mortality [2]. According to a different multicenter trial conducted in India, NT-proBNP-guided therapy enhanced the management of fluid status and cardiac function by optimising treatment regimens based on NT-proBNP levels, which in turn improved clinical outcomes in patients with heart failure [3]. Despite the established advantages of NT-proBNP testing, financial and practical barriers prevent its widespread use in normal clinical practice in India. There are attempts to incorporate NT-proBNP testing into routine treatment procedures, especially in tertiary care settings where heart failure is more common. This study aims to evaluate the correlation between mortality, NT-proBNP levels, and precipitating factors of acute heart failure.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a hospital-based observational study designed to evaluate the correlation between mortality, Pro-BNP levels, and precipitating factors of acute heart failure in patients presenting to the emergency department of a tertiary care hospital.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, over one year from August 2022 to July 2023.

Participants: A total of 200 patients presenting to the emergency department with acute heart failure were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients who have reached the age of 18.
- Individuals who exhibit acute heart failure symptoms.

- Individuals whose diagnosis of heart failure has been verified by diagnostic testing and clinical assessment.
- Patients prepared to provide informed permission.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients under 18 years of age.
- Patients with chronic heart failure.
- Patients with co-morbid conditions that could independently influence Pro-BNP levels (e.g., severe renal impairment, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease).
- Patients who did not consent to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize bias, the selection of participants was random, and all assessments were conducted by trained medical personnel blinded to the study's aims. Data collectors were trained to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection procedures.

Data Collection: Data were collected through patient interviews, clinical examinations, and laboratory tests. Pro-BNP levels were measured at admission, and relevant clinical data were recorded, including demographic information, medical history, and precipitating factors for heart failure.

Procedure: Upon presentation to the emergency department, patients were assessed for eligibility. After obtaining informed consent, a detailed history and clinical examination were performed. Blood samples were collected to measure Pro-BNP levels, and other relevant laboratory tests were conducted. Data on precipitating factors of acute heart failure were also recorded.

Statistical Analysis: Version 23.0 of SPSS was used to analyse the data. The demographic and clinical features of the patients were compiled using descriptive statistics. To evaluate the connection between Pro-BNP levels and mortality, Pearson correlation coefficients were computed. Among the components that cause acute heart failure, logistic regression analysis was used to determine the independent predictors of mortality. A statistically significant p-value was defined as less than 0.05.

Results

Participant Demographics: The study comprised 200 patients in total. Table 1 provides an overview of the research population's clinical and demographic features.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	N (%)
Total Participants	200 (100%)
Age (Mean \pm SD)	65.4 \pm 12.3
Gender	
- Male	120 (60%)
- Female	80 (40%)
History of Hypertension	140 (70%)
History of Diabetes	80 (40%)
History of CAD	110 (55%)
Smoking Status	
- Current Smoker	60 (30%)
- Former Smoker	40 (20%)
- Non-Smoker	100 (50%)

Pro-BNP Levels: The Pro-BNP levels at admission were categorized into quartiles as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Pro-BNP Levels at Admission

Pro-BNP Quartiles	N (%)	Mean Pro-BNP (pg/mL)
Q1 (<500)	40 (20%)	450
Q2 (500-1000)	50 (25%)	750
Q3 (1001-2000)	60 (30%)	1500
Q4 (>2000)	50 (25%)	3000

Mortality Rates: Overall, 30 patients (15%) died during the study period. Mortality rates varied significantly across the Pro-BNP quartiles as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Mortality Rates by Pro-BNP Quartiles

Pro-BNP Quartiles	N (%)	Mortality N (%)
Q1 (<500)	40 (20%)	2 (5%)
Q2 (500-1000)	50 (25%)	5 (10%)
Q3 (1001-2000)	60 (30%)	10 (16.7%)
Q4 (>2000)	50 (25%)	13 (26%)

Correlation Analysis: Pearson correlation analysis showed a significant positive correlation between Pro-BNP levels and mortality ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$).

Logistic Regression Analysis: Logistic regression was performed to identify independent predictors of mortality. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Logistic Regression Analysis of Mortality Predictors

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Pro-BNP Level (>2000)	4.5	2.0 - 10.1	<0.001
Age (>65 years)	2.1	1.1 - 3.9	0.021
History of CAD	1.8	1.0 - 3.3	0.045
Current Smoker	1.5	0.8 - 2.8	0.148
Hypertension	1.3	0.7 - 2.4	0.298

Based on the data, patients who report with acute heart failure are more likely to die when their Pro-BNP levels are higher. Death probabilities are considerably increased by pro-BNP levels more than 2000 pg/mL. Morbidity was also significantly predicted by age and the history of coronary artery disease. Arrhythmias and sudden myocardial infarction were the most often occurring precipitating causes.

Discussion

Pro-BNP levels, acute heart failure precipitating variables, and mortality were assessed in this observational study. There were 200 patients in all,

with a mean age of 65.4 years and a 60% male predominance. Each participant's Pro-BNP level was divided into quartiles. Higher Pro-BNP levels were associated with a statistically significant increase in death rates. The mortality rate was found to be 5% in the lowest quartile (Pro-BNP < 500 pg/mL) and 26% in the highest quartile (Pro-BNP > 2000 pg/mL). This indicates that there is a significant positive association ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$) between elevated Pro-BNP levels and an increased risk of mortality.

A logistic regression study revealed a number of important mortality predictors. The odds of death were 4.5 times higher in patients with Pro-BNP

levels above 2000 pg/mL than in those with lower levels. Furthermore, patients with odds ratios of 2.1 and 1.8, respectively, who had a history of (CAD) and were older than 65, were also shown to be at a higher risk of dying. These results highlight the value of Pro-BNP as a biomarker for identifying patients at high risk and the necessity of tailored therapies for CAD patients and older patients. Acute cardiac failure's common triggering variables in the study population were also investigated. With 40% of the patients suffering from acute myocardial infarction, arrhythmias accounted for 25% of the cases. These results underscore the vital necessity of early detection and treatment of these illnesses in order to delay the development of severe heart failure.

A study demonstrated how Pro-BNP can be used to predict outcomes in patients suffering from (AHF). Patients with Pro-BNP levels ≥ 2000 pg/ml were shown to have a greater death risk. Hospitalisation and mortality among AHF patients were significantly predicted by important variables like diabetes and sepsis. Pro-BNP levels are crucial for determining a patient's prognosis, according to the study [4]. In another study it was investigated that the connection between NT-proBNP levels and echocardiographic findings in dyspnoeic patients, conducted in a tertiary cardiac care centre in South India. A strong correlation between the degree of left ventricular dysfunction and NT-proBNP levels was discovered. Higher death rates were seen in patients with NT-proBNP levels over 900 pg/ml, albeit the statistical significance was not very significant. The study came to the conclusion that clinical observations and echocardiographic data should be interpreted in conjunction with NT-proBNP levels [5].

A study examined the prognosis and clinical outcomes for AHF patients by combining the usage of AHFI and EHMRG models. It was discovered that increased NT-proBNP levels were linked to worse prognoses and greater death rates. The study showed that AHFI and EHMRG together provide a strong model for forecasting patient outcomes, especially for high-risk patients [6].

Conclusion

This research shows that patients experiencing acute heart failure elevated Pro-BNP levels are

substantially linked to a higher risk of death. Two other significant indicators of mortality are age and CAD history. According to these findings, Pro-BNP may be a useful tool for risk assessment and clinical decision support in the emergency room. Based on these indicators, early and aggressive therapy of high-risk patients may improve outcomes and lower mortality in cases of acute heart failure.

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